

Sleep-stage dynamics predicts current sleep-disordered-breathing and future cardiovascular risk

M. Bechny^{1,2}, *Y. Tomita*³, *M. Scutari*⁴, *J. van der Meer*⁵, *M. Schmidt*⁵, *C. Bassetti*⁵, *A. Tzovara*^{1,5}, *A. Kishij* *⁶, *F. Faraci* *²

¹University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland, ²SUPSI-MeDiTech, Lugano-Viganello, Switzerland, ³Sleep Center, Toranomon Hospital, Tokyo, Japan, ⁴Istituto Dalle Molle di Studi sull'Intelligenza Artificiale (IDSIA), Lugano-Viganello, Switzerland, ⁵Inselspital, Universitätsspital Bern, Bern, Switzerland, ⁶The University of Tokyo, Tokyo, Japan

Type

Presentation type: Oral presentation

Please consider this abstract for the Asian Society of Sleep Medicine (ASSM) meeting to be held on Saturday and Sunday, September 6-7, 2025.: No

General data

Topic: Sleep Breathing Disorders

Secondary topic: Epidemiology

Abstract text

Introduction: Sleep-disordered breathing (SDB) is a well-established contributor to cardiovascular morbidity and mortality, including hypertension, stroke, and heart failure^{1,2}. In addition to its respiratory effects, SDB disrupts sleep-macrostructure³ and, as emerging evidence suggests, alters sleep-stage dynamics⁴⁻⁶. This implies that both macrostructure and dynamics may be statistically linked with cardiovascular risk, as they can reflect downstream effects of SDB—thus enabling predictive modelling. Previous studies have primarily examined static macrostructural features, such as total-sleep-time (TST) or N3/REM durations, concerning cardiovascular outcomes⁷⁻⁹. However, the temporal organisation of sleep—specifically, transitions between stages—remains largely unexplored as a predictor of long-term cardiovascular risk. To address this gap, we present the first study evaluating whether sleep-stage dynamics can predict future cardiovascular outcomes in a large prospective cohort.

Materials and methods: We analyzed data from the Sleep Heart Health Study (SHHS)¹⁰, a prospective cohort of SDB-untreated individuals, examining the links between SDB and cardiovascular health. 5791 participants underwent baseline (SHHS1) in-home polysomnography (PSG); 2651 repeated it on-average 5 years later (SHHS2), and were followed for over 10 years. The PSG was scored into five stages (W, N1-3, REM), and apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) was calculated using the "recommended" definition, consistent with AASM guidelines (v2.2, 2015). We focused on 2581 SHHS1 participants without prior cardiovascular events or sleep-altering medications (e.g., antidepressants, diuretics, alpha/beta-blockers). The primary outcome was the first occurrence of a composite cardiovascular event: heart failure, stroke, myocardial infarction, angina, or cardiovascular surgical procedure since baseline. Predictors included: 25 (5x5) sleep-stage transition proportions, conventional sleep markers (e.g., TST), BMI, smoking status, and demographics. We used Random Forest (RF) for SDB detection and Random Survival Forest¹¹ (RSF) for cardiovascular risk prediction, both non-parametric methods robust to predictors' multicollinearity and non-linear effects.

Results: RF model for detecting moderate-to-severe SDB (AHI>15) achieved cross-validated ROC>75%, with stable performance across REM/NREM subtypes and strong generalization (ROC>70%) even to patients with medications or prior events, suggesting that SDB can be accurately predicted from sleep-stage features and demographics alone. RSF predicting future cardiovascular outcomes achieved concordance indices and time-dependent-ROC >75% across 1-10 year horizons, with significant log-rank separation (p<0.05, for high- vs. low-risk groups). Analysis of partial effects confirmed known risk factors like age and smoking, while revealing novel U-shaped risk profiles for many predictors—suggesting optimal ranges with increased risk at both extremes—including BMI (~25), TST (~350 min), and sleep-stage continuities such as N1-to-N1 (~2%), N2-to-N2 (~40%), N3-to-N3 (~10-30%), and REM-to-REM (~20%). Specific atypical transitions, such as R-to-N3 and N3-to-N1, increased risk by >10% per single nightly occurrence; N3-to-REM and W-to-N3 were associated with ~5% increased risk when occurring ≥2 times per night.

Conclusions: Sleep-stage dynamics are sensitive markers for both SDB and long-term cardiovascular risk. Our findings, including confirmed effects of N3/REM^{7,8}, suggest novel risk markers based on sleep-stage transitions, providing deeper physiological insight than traditional macrostructure measures. While cardiovascular risk can be accurately predicted from sleep, further analysis is needed to design optimal treatment and sleep management interventions.

Acknowledgments:

*Co-senior authorship

1. [10.1164/rccm.200911-1746OC](https://doi.org/10.1164/rccm.200911-1746OC)
2. [10.1378/chest.10-2223](https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.10-2223)
3. [10.1007/BF03339872](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03339872)
4. [10.1038/sj.npp.1300146](https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.npp.1300146)
5. [10.1371/journal.pone.0011356](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0011356)
6. [10.1038/s41598-025-97172-3](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-97172-3)
7. [10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.111.174409](https://doi.org/10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.111.174409)
8. [10.1001/jamaneurol.2020.2108](https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaneurol.2020.2108)
9. [10.1007/s11886-022-01816-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11886-022-01816-z)
10. [10.1093/sleep/20.12.1077](https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/20.12.1077)
11. [10.1214/08-AOAS169](https://doi.org/10.1214/08-AOAS169)

1. I confirm that the abstract and that all information is correct: Yes
 2. I confirm that the abstract constitutes consent to publication: Yes
 3. I confirm that I submit this abstract on behalf of all authors.: Yes
- I understand that the presenting author **MUST** register for the congress: Yes